

MICROBIOLOGICAL AND MOLECULAR INVESTIGATIONS OF *Salmonella* ISOLATED IN MEAT PRODUCTS IN DUHOK PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT

Salmonellosis continues to be a major public health problem worldwide. It also contributes to negative economic impacts due to the cost of surveillance investigation, treatment and prevention of illness. As such, research on *Salmonella* has gained great of interest and concern from scientists. To study the presences of *Salmonella* isolate generally in meat products that were collected from local shops and markets in Duhok Province. A total of 200 samples, 50 samples from each of ground meat; Shawarma; burger and kebab were examined from July till September 2014 in veterinary laboratories in Duhok Province. Samples were checked for the incidence of *Salmonella* isolate. by applying bacteriological, biochemical and RT-PCR tests. It was revealed that 2 (4%) of minced meat , 1 (2%) of burger ,0% (0/50) of shawarma, and 0% (0/50) of kebab were detected for the presence of *Salmonella* .Higher rate of *Salmonella* was seen in minced meat and burger ,on the other hand *Salmonella* were not reported in shawarma and kebab.

INTRODUCTION

Salmonella species have been regarded as one of the most common causes of food borne pathogen all around the world (Chalghoumi *et al.*, 2009). According to (Ruban *et al.*, 2010 and Chashni *et al.*, 2009) the main sources for transmitting *Salmonella* species to human are meat and poultry products with 40 % of the clinical cases attributed to the consumption of eggs and poultry products.

It is estimated that the food-borne disease ,such as, *E.coli*, *Salmonella*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Clostridium perfringens* causes 93.8million illness each year and 155000 death annually worldwide(Majowicz *et al.*,2010) . Consequently, food poisoning outbreaks are prevalent in many regions of the world.

The infective dose of *Salmonella* can be as low as 15 to 20 cells, depending upon age and health of host. Globally, *Salmonella* is one of the most common causes of enteric (intestinal) infections and it is the second most common bacterial foodborne cause after *Campylobacter* illness (Tajbakhsh *et al.*, 2012).

Meat products are gaining popularity because they represent quick easily prepared meals of low price from one side, and render the processors to convert the various types of meat into unified

products. On the other side, meat products are liable to harbour different types of microorganisms through a long chain of handling, processing, distribution and storage as well as preparation. Within this respect, they are considered as serious sources of food borne diseases and have been frequently linked to major outbreaks of food poisoning all over the world (Ahmed *et al.*, 1999).

Salmonella can contaminate ready to eat (RTE) products in the ways of under processing when the lethality treatment is not adequate to eliminate the *Salmonella* and by cross contamination (United States Department of Agriculture and Food Safety and Inspection Service 2011). In this research, samples from red meat and food samples that are coming from various types of RTE meat products including shawarma, meat kebab and burgers were tested, for detection and isolation of *Salmonella*, by culturing and biochemical techniques and then they were confirmed by RT- PCR methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two hundred samples of meat products that distributed between (50 kebabs, 50 ground meats, 50 Shawarma, and 50 burgers) were collected from local markets and from the slaughter unit in Duhok province of Iraq. The sampling period was

from July to September 2014 for investigation of the prevalence of *Salmonella* in meat products.

Microbiological investigations

Twenty five grams of meat products for each sample were suspended in 225 ml of Nutrient broth and incubated for 24 h at 37°C for pre-enrichment. One milliliter of pre-enrichment broth was transferred to 10 ml of Rappaport broth (CONDA, Spain), (Selective Enrichment) and incubated for 24 h at 42°C. One loop-full of Rappaport broth was streaked onto *Salmonella-Shigella* (S-S) agar (CONDA, Spain) and Brilliant green agar (CONDA, Spain) (Selective media), XLD agar (CONDA, Spain) and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. Following that, the suspected *Salmonella* colonies were transferred simultaneously to ABC chromogenic agar (CONDA, Spain), and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C (10). The suspected *Salmonella* colonies appeared green pale color on ABC agar. Then the colonies

were re-purified on Blood agar for API 20E (RapID ONE system, remel, USA) test. In addition, the suspected colonies were confirmed as *Salmonella* by API test and RT- PCR.

DNA Extraction

The DNA from *Salmonella* colony was extracted from the sweep of few colonies grown on ABC Agar plates by boiling method. Briefly, loopfull of *Salmonella* from agar plates was suspended in 100 µl of sterile de-ionized water in a 1.5 ml eppendorf tube and a bacterial suspension was vortexed. The bacterial suspension was boiled at 95-100°C for 10 min and centrifuged at 10,000x g for 10 min. The supernatant was used as a DNA template for PCR (Nessa *et al.*, 2007). Purification of DNA was achieved by using a genomic DNA purification kit (Qiagen, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instruction. The DNA was measured by using Nanodrop Spectrophotometer QIAXpert (QIAGEN) and stored at 4°C.

Table (1): RT-PCR conditions and cycling for *Salmonella* detection.

Stage	Temperature	Time	Cycles
Holding stage	37°C	4 minute	1
Holding stage	95°C	5 minute	1
Denaturation	95°C	5 second	50
Annealing	60°C	60 second	50

Confirmation of Samples with Real Time PCR Technique

Screening of suspected *Salmonella* that isolated microbiologically were conducted according to Foodproof® *Salmonella* detection kit (Biotecon Diagnostics, Catalog) which is PCR kit for the qualitative detection of *Salmonella monocytogens*, using Real-Time PCR instruments. In this method a fluorescent dye is used to follow the PCR amplification in real-time and can be used to detect the amplified products from a number of genes at the same time (Bhagwat *et al.*, 2003). The Real-Time PCR was done with a final volume of 25 µl of reaction mixture in each well of a 96-well plate, in which containing of 20 µl of PCR Master Mix (provided) and 5 µl of DNA template, beside positive and negative control were run. The DNA from samples was amplified in the standard mode running (2 hours) on a 7500 fast real-time PCR machine (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA). The reactions were run according to the thermocycling conditions as

defined in table 1. The amplification results were visualized and analyzed during the last 50 cycles of the amplifications using the 7500 fast software V.1.4.0 (Applied Biosystems) with the thermocycler AB 7500 fast (Applied Biosystem, Foster City, CA, USA).

RESULTS

The present study identified the *Salmonella* isolates in meat products by using cultural, biochemical, and molecular method

Microbiological Results

The microbiological results from 200 meat products are presented in (Table 2) From 200 meat samples, black colonies on S-S and XLD agars were isolated from the 20 suspected samples after enrichment and selective plating and confirmed as *Salmonella* by using biochemical tests. The isolated *Salmonella* specimens were tested by API test. The results showed that burger has the highest percentage of *salmonella* with 11(22%) compared to 2(8%) of shawarma (Table 2).

Table (2): Positive samples for Culture and Biochemical methods

Product Type	No of sample	Number of positive sample by	
		Culture method	Biochemical method
Ground meat	50	4 (8%)	2 (4%)
Burger	50	11 (22%)	3 (6%)
Shawarma	50	2 (8%)	0 (0%)
Kebab	50	3 (6%)	3 (6%)
Total	200	20 (11.11%)	8 (4.4%)

PCR Results

It can be seen that, only few samples showed positive for *salmonella* by RT-PCR method (3 out of 200 samples). Interestingly, the ground meat positive samples were

doubled than burgers (4% compared to 2%) and this made the first as highest rate for *salmonella* (Table 3). There was no detection of *salmonella* isolates in both shawarma and kebab meat by RT-PCR assay.

Table (3): Positive samples by RT-PCR

Product Type	No of sample	Positive Sample by PCR
Ground meat	50	2 (4%)
Hamburger	50	1 (2%)
Shawarma	50	0 (0%)
Kebab	50	0 (0%)
Total	200	3 (1.5%)

It is clear that the threshold (Ct) values were varied depending on several factors including the concentration of DNA templates (Figure 1). The higher concentrations of the DNA were quantified at the lower Ct values and vice versa. However,

the samples with a Ct value up to 40 considered as a positive sample for Salmonellosis. Nevertheless, no amplification can be seen in the well of negative control, assuming that the primers were specific.

Fig. (1): Amplification plots of *Salmonella* isolates Fluorescence versus cycle number. The figure demonstrates that the three positive samples amplifying, strong band in positive control and shows no band in negative control.

DISCUSSION

The infection rate of *Salmonella* in all meat products was 1.5 % using RT-PCR assay (Table 3) which is somehow disagreed with some other studies such as (Little *et al.*, 1999)7%.The highest percentage of *Salmonella* isolates was seen in ground meat and burger 2 (4%) and 1 (2.5%) respectively, which lower than results of (Hassanien *et al.*,2004) 4%. Interesting results can be seen with kebab and Shawarma *Salmonella* isolates, were not reported in that sample. However, in other finding conducted by (Hassanien *et al.*,2004) and his colleague there was up to 10 % in the incidences of *Salmonella* isolates in such cited food . Failure to detect *Salmonella* isolates, in RTE in the current research is resemble to the finding conducted in Wales by (Meldrum *et al.*, 2006) and Nigeria (Umoh and Odoaba *et al.*, 1999). Higher rates of *Salmonella* isolates were seen in ground meat in contrast to other food product these outcome may be attributed to the physical conditions of burger and ground meat (minced and less compact products) (Cossi *et al.*,2013) and the pre-cooked status without any heat that keep them more liable to bacterial contamination. Lower rates of *Salmonella* isolates. in kebab and shawarma can be due to heat treatment during manufacture and

presence of chemical preservatives (Hosein *et al.*, 2008 ; Kuhn *et al.*, 2011).

Turning into the comparison between API and PCR for identification of *Salmonella*, it is worthwhile mentioning that isolation and accurate identification of *Salmonella* is challenging in clinical microbiology (Hoorfar *et al.*, 1999). API 20E system, which depends on biochemical substrate utilization for classification, has always been applied as the standard of comparison for identification of members of the family Enterbacteriaceae (O'Hara *et al.*, 1992). As it was clear from the results, the same result were found for both API and PCR for detection of *Salmonella* in ground meat and Shawarma, but the scenario were different for burger where reported *Salmonella* isolates is less (Table 3), and even not detected by PCR in case of kebab. (Robinson *et al.*, 1995) stated that API 20E has not often gained satisfactory outcome. Rather than depending on phenotypic traits, detection of bacteria like *Salmonella* can be improved by recognition of genotypic characteristics, e.g., polymerase chain reaction (PCR) techniques targeting gene sequences unique to *Salmonella* (Vanechoutte and Van Eldere *et al.*, 1997).

Recently study have highlighted that meat products such as minced beef and burger are significant source for bacterial contamination and

infectious such as *salmonella* pathogen and may cause serious illness. Although our result show that Shawarma and Kebab have a lower rate of contamination compared to minced and burger. We still have to consider as a cause of gastrointestinal illness. To decrease the risk of acquiring *salmonella* poisoning from food and meat by cook meat to safe temperature and wash any kitchen utensils with hot soapy water after contact with raw meat.

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